

Improving the efficiency of inland waterborne transport in the Rhine-Alpine corridor

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Abstract

This paper presents the first step to the simulation model of the container Inland Waterborne Transportation (IWT) system that is being developed within the NOVIMOVE framework. In doing this, the paper analyzes the market developments and identifies the current situation and challenges of container barge transport regarding both deepsea and inland terminals. To address these challenges, a Discrete Event Simulation (DES) model for the barge logistics system is proposed. This model will allow for a detailed analysis of the impact of the different innovations (such as mobile terminals, vessel trains, cargo reconstruction, and smart navigation) that are being developed within the NOVIMOVE framework. Hence, the current paper sets the background of the model by establishing the DES model architecture, the system boundary, data requirements and the key performance indicators (KPIs) that are established within the model.

Keywords: Discrete event simulation, Key performance indicators, container transport, Inland waterborne transport.

1. Introduction

Inland waterborne transport (IWT) is a major key-holder for unlocking the congestion in seaports, terminals, road networks and access to urban areas, besides being the main factor in reducing CO₂emissions in freight transport. Inland waterways have so far contributed to the development and performance of port activities. There has been a great emergence of container transportation through inland navigation over the years. IWT container transport can offer an efficient transport service to different regions, which are close to rivers such as the Rhine and the Meuse as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Important European IWT network (Rhine and Maas).

Source: Loos & Jones, (2011)

IWT transport offers various benefits such as cost-efficient means of accessing the hinterland, economies of scale and attraction of several shippers and carriers to the port (Shobayo & van Hassel, 2019). These days, barge hinterland transportation has become an important mode of transportation in large seaports with inner connections for three main reasons. Firstly, it serves as a cost- and environment-efficient model of transport as compared with other modes. Secondly, it helps to reduce congestion in inland infrastructure and other environmental impacts associated with hinterland transportation. Finally, it creates a network of inland terminals, which offers shippers an alternative for road transport to and from the deep-sea ports, thereby leading to reduced freight transport cost.

However, there are some main challenges in further developing the IWT transport in North-Western Europe. These challenges, along with the possible solutions to overcome the challenges, are researched within the NOVIMOVE¹ project. The effectiveness of the proposed solutions is determined by making use of a simulation model in which both the current IWT container logistics system on the Rhine-Alpine corridor as well as the impact of the different innovations that are aimed at improving container barge transport in North-Western Europe are included. Based on this, the main objective of this paper is to set the framework and provide a detailed requirement of the model. The rest of the paper is structured as follows: section two focuses on the market description, challenges of container barging and the innovations that will be tested to help address these challenges. . Section three focuses on the modelling method to use within NOVIMOVE. Section four specifies the framework of the modelling approach. Section five identifies the data source and requirements needed for the model. Section six specifies the main output also known as the key performance indicators (KPIs) within the model. Finally, section seven concludes the paper.

2. Market description and challenges of container barging in Europe

A limited number of countries in Europe have major connectivity to the IWT network. Nearly 100% of all container transport on European inland waterways takes place in only four countries: the Netherlands, Belgium, Germany and France. The majority of the IWT container transport has its origin and destination in these countries. Hence, the Alpine-Rhine corridor is important for the economy of these countries, since it connects various major inland and deep-sea ports such as Duisburg, Antwerp and Rotterdam. The quarterly performance, defined as the number of TEUs, of three out of the four countries is always above 400,000 TEU as revealed in Figure 2, with France having the lowest transport performance. Other countries, such as Luxemburg, Austria, Romania, have relatively less TEU volumes compared with the above-mentioned countries.

The overall trend between 2007 and 2020 revealed the increasing use of IWT for container transport. The reason for this increase, according to Sys, Van de Voorde, Vanelslander, & van Hassel, (2020), is the growth of container transport especially in the ports of Antwerp and Rotterdam in this period. Irrespective of this increased use of IWT, road transport still has a significant share in container freight transport, as seen in Figure 3. As seen, road transport has a dominant share with an average of 76% over the identified years. IWT, meanwhile, has an average of 18% in the EU countries. The significant share of road transport and the corresponding societal challenges associated with this mode of transport motivates European countries with access to the IWT network to shift cargoes from the road to IWT.

¹ NOVIMOVE is the acronym for: Novel inland waterway transport concepts for moving freight effectively. A project that is funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 Program under grant agreement n° 858508.

Figure 4 shows the share of tonnes of cargo being transported in a container. From this figure, it can be concluded that 1 out of every 6 tonnes transported by rail, is a container tonne (a tonne of cargo being transported in a container). For IWT, this is 1 out of 16 tonnes. What is interesting to see is that this share grows from 7% in 2010 to almost 10% in 2017. This implies that the importance of container transport on the EU inland waterways is increasing.

Figure 2: Quarterly container transport performance in top 4 IWW countries (in TEU, 2015-2018).
Source: Based on Eurostat (2020).

Figure 3: European modal split of freight transport.
Source: Based on Eurostat (2020).

Figure 4: Container transport by mode as a share of the total freight transport in Europe.

Source: Based on Eurostat (2020).

Despite the importance of container barge transport and the potential for more growth, the sector faces several operations which have affected its competitiveness. These challenges begin with the arrangements between the shipper and the shipping agents, and further extend to the operations, handling and navigability and capacity utilization of inland container barges.

The first challenge of container barge transport starts with the agreement between shippers and shipping agents about the arrangements of transport conditions and delivery options to and from the port. Generally, barge transportation is cheaper than trucks (offered by inland terminals), enticing shippers with a large volume of containers to make use of the barge transport service. This has led not only to the growth of container transport but also to high expectations that are similar to that of road transport (fast, reliable and timely). Unfortunately, container barges have been unable to meet these expectations partly due to the level of coordination and agreement that is needed from various parties in the transport chain.

Secondly, inland barges have small call sizes (<20 TEUs) and have no contractual relationship with deep-sea terminals. Due to the small call sizes, they have to make several calls to different terminals (6-8 calls) but because they have no contractual relationship with the deep-sea terminals, they need to wait for available wharf and crane facilities at each terminal, thereby disrupting their planning and leading to high congestion level in the port.

Thirdly, container barges mostly operate with an average load factor². This means that container barges are often not loaded to full capacities, leading to sub-optimal use of the IWT capacity, and terminal infrastructures. Due to the low load factors, deep-sea terminals have little incentive to allocate terminal resources to handle these vessels, as it often leads to low productivity and inefficient utilization of terminal resources, which are mainly designed to handle the deep-sea vessels.

² The load factor is the ratio of the average load to the total vehicle freight capacity (containers, vans, lorries, train wagons, ships)

More so, the varying water levels along the Rhine³ have had a significantly negative impact on the occupation rate of container barges, thereby influencing transport price. It is observed that the transport price of freight within IWT is unstable and sometimes unsustainable for the vessel owners and barge operators. This is due to different factors such as the transport supply, transport demand, stiff competition from other transport modes and the varying water levels. According to Sys et al. (2020), freight prices in France and Belgium are often lower than in other countries with IWT in Western Europe. The possible reason for this, according to the researchers, is the combination of transport supply (which is often characterized by many smaller but older inland vessels as displayed in Table 1), transport demand (which is often characterized by low-value goods) and competition from other transport modes.

Table 1: Western-European dry cargo fleet (2015).

Size	Number	Tonnage	Average age
<55 meter	755	321,910	78.18
55-86 meter	2,619	2,933,584	59.15
>86 meter	1,009	2,865,284	14.94
Total	4,383	6,120,778	

Source: van Hassel, (2015)

The nature of the Rhine causes a widely varying water level across the different seasons in a year; meanwhile, vessels sailing along the river must adhere to a sailing depth which is usually determined by fixed tide gauges⁴ installed along the Rhine. These gauges display erratic water levels as seen in Figure 5 (water level for Kaub gauge). The figure further reveals that there is a frequent occurrence of extended low water level along the Rhine in recent years, with the year 2018 experiencing the longest period of very low water levels between 2003 and 2019. The impact of this is revealed by the drop in TEU transported for the Netherlands, Germany and France.

Figure 5: Water level along the Rhine (Kaub).

Source: Sys et al., (2020)

³ The Rhine is both a glacier river (high water in the summer due to melting snow) and a rain river

⁴ The two most important gauges along the Rhine are the Cologne gauge (located along the Dutch-German border to Cologne) and the Kaub gauge (located along Cologne to Basel).

The frequent low water levels limit sailing possibility and reduce vessel capacity utilization, thereby making container shipping via IWT more difficult and expensive.

Finally, there is the problem of planning, coordinating, scheduling and navigating container barges. Due to the complexity involved in planning and coordinating the schedules of container barges concerning terminal visits and the passing of the locks and bridges, it becomes quite challenging to anticipate the next moves of the barges and adequately plan their schedules. To address this, effective management and cooperation of cargo flows, vessels, deepsea terminals and waterway infrastructure become necessary. This would ensure a compressed logistics system where individual stakeholders manage their operations and at the same time obtain information from the entire stakeholder network.

To address the different identified challenges, different innovations are being tested within NOVIMOVE. These innovations include;

- Cargo reconstruction to help improve the current load factors of vessels.
- Mobile terminals and vessel trains to help improve IWT port operations.
- Smart navigation to help generate an optimized vessel route and speed based on actual water depth, current vessel performance, bridge, and lock availability.
- Dynamic scheduling to help recommend optimized opening times of bridges and locks based on expected vessel arrival times, other relevant traffic, and bridge/lock capacity.
- New vessel designs to help address the effect of low water levels.

These innovations will be integrated into the NOVIMOVE simulation model in modular ways (to be able to examine the impact of each of them) and will be capable of interacting with each other. Within the model, agents will be created that will handle the communication with these modules.

3. Modelling method

In this section, an overview of the modelling methods that are considered for use is given, highlighting the advantages and disadvantages, capabilities, and limitations of all methods.

Table 2: Overview of the different modelling methods

Simulation type	Advantages	Disadvantages
Agent-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capable of simulating complicated, non-linear, discontinuous, or discrete interactions between agents • Agents are autonomous units processing information and exchanging this information with other agents to make an independent decision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The model must be built at the right level of description for every phenomenon • Computationally expensive
Continuous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High level of detail • Able to simulate systems that are described by differential equations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computationally expensive • Difficult to model complex behaviour
Discrete event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable when time evolution plays an important role • Computationally inexpensive • Various levels of detail and complexity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not optimize the solution • It May become computationally expensive if the number of entities exceeds a certain limit
Systems Dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excellent for closed-loop systems • Focuses on flows around networks • Behaviour is predictable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not suited for complex systems with a high level of detail. • Deterministic in nature

Optimization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gives the optimal solution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computationally expensive • Computational time is not constant • The optimal solution cannot always be found within a workable timespan • Modelling has limitations
Heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computationally inexpensive • Results can be interpreted relatively easily • The result can come close to the optimal solution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will not give the optimal solution • Requires knowledge and experience to apply the heuristics effectively

From Table 2, it can be concluded that the choice of simulation method will mostly depend on the level of detail and flexibility required for the simulation. Furthermore, the computational effort for the model to run will be a determining factor. Based on this, the discrete event simulation (DES) model typically offer a suitable option. The requirements of the DES are specified below:

- Represent the IWT container logistics chain, including all identified actors, from seaport terminals to inland port terminals and the end destination at a distribution centre along the Rhine-Alpine corridor
- Represent the other transport modes (road and rail), with higher abstraction.
- Modular architecture approach.
- Calculates the impact of the NOVIMOVE main ideas and innovations on the overall performance
- Gamification of the NOVIMOVE innovations (logistics, navigation, and innovative vessel concepts) for education and dissemination.

From this, it becomes apparent that the simulation needs a large-scale network and may require some simplifications to meet the requirement for serious gaming exercise. As earlier mentioned, part of the requirements of the simulation model is to create a serious game that can be used by universities as part of their education program. The specific requirements of this game include:

- *Usability*: user should be able to set up scenarios⁵ within a relatively short time without being an expert user of the model. Different users must be able to work together when setting up and analysing scenarios.
- *Runtime*: scenarios must be capable of running within 15 minutes to be used during interactive workshops.
- *Result analysis*: to ensure an efficient analysis of the model results, a high-level dashboard with an overview of specific KPI's for different scenarios.

To meet these requirements, the model will be equipped with a web-interface supporting multiple users at the same time. Furthermore, specific user roles, such as barge operator, terminal operator, forwarder/freight forwarder/logistics service provider, are defined. Expert-user should have unlimited access to the input parameters, while other users may be restricted to create a simpler workflow for

⁵ University of Antwerp and Delft University of Technology wants to use the model for the following exercise: Optimize the IWT Rhine-Alpine corridor in a group of students whereas each student has controls over a subdomain of the model. In this situation each student has a specific user role with a dedicated user interface, allowing him to play the game from his individual perspective. A supervisor user, could have all model controls, in order to take advise from the other students on their "local" optimized solutions.

setting up scenarios. Furthermore, the runtime can be reduced by disabling parts of the model and focusing on the specific part of the Rhine-Alpine corridor. Finally, to ensure efficient result analysis, a high-level specific dashboard with high-level KPIs will be created. By default, large log-files will be disabled. Users will be able to enable them if required. A parallel coordinates chart will be implemented to compare scenarios over multiple KPIs.

4. DES modelling framework

The DES model will represent the logistics system operations over time and is capable of representing in detail the IWT container logistics chain from seaport terminals to the distribution centres, while also representing the road and rail network, and incorporating, processing and demonstrating the impact of the different innovative ideas on the overall performance of the IWT container logistics chain. To achieve this, a model architecture and system boundary are developed for the elements within the container IWT sector. This is displayed in Figure 6.

Figure 6: System boundary for container IWT

Source: Own creation

The system boundaries of the model are determined by taking into account the insights that were obtained from the market development, surveys and workshops with the stakeholders. The system boundary in Figure 6 is divided into three main blocks: the demand side, the supply side and the NOVIMOVE innovations. The demand side focuses on cargo flows from the shipper/logistics service providers and the factors that might affect the volume of containers being transported. In this block, economic or market disruptions affect the level of import and export of goods, which in turn affect the flow of containerized cargoes, thereby affecting the volume of containers that are being transported by the shippers/logistics service providers.

The flow of container transport is measured at a disaggregated regional level of countries within the Alpine-Rhine corridor (The Netherlands, Belgium, Germany, Luxembourg and Switzerland). Containers can be transported by three modes (road, rail and IWT). The volume of containers transported via any of these modes is dependent on key variables that influence shippers transport choice. These variables include the transport cost, service reliability in the transport mode, the lead/transit time, transport mode availability and frequency of transport service.

The supply side shows the modal split, which is based on the transport decision of the shippers and the rail/road option for the terminals (deep-sea and inland) and distribution centres. For this, the network flow from the deep-sea terminal to the distribution centres is represented. Due to the focus of this study on IWT, a separate sub-block is created for the flow and interaction of the different actors. In this block, the interactions among terminal operators (deep-sea and inland), barge operators and waterway managers are represented, as well as how these interactions affect container barge handling and sailing in terminals and ports. Furthermore, some elements affecting the operations of the different actors are identified. For terminal operators, these elements include handling capacity, night opening, call sizes, handling space, handling operations and berth occupancy rate. For barge operators, the elements include call sizes, investment cost, operational cost, water levels, terminal visits and sailing schedules. Elements for waterway managers meanwhile include flexibility in schedule planning, bridge level and management, water levels management, locks management and real-time data management.

The third main block is the different NOVIMOVE innovations that will improve the current container barge transport situation and increase the mode share of container IWT transport. The innovations that will be researched include the development and use of mobile terminals, vessel trains, cargo reconstruction, developing a smart navigation system, innovative vessel concept and the development of a decision support system for stakeholder interaction.

As can be seen in the figure, the DES model boundary is handling a complex environment where events occur in sequence. The model of this environment contains uncertainties, constraints, and interactions among the different events, hence the DES model will represent the logistics system (behaviour, functions, and abstract or physical properties) of the container IWT system based on the system boundary specified. The simulations will thus represent the logistics system operation over time, and the main model capabilities are as follows:

- Representing in detail the IWT container logistics chain from seaport terminals to inland port terminals and the final destination at a distribution centre along the Rhine-Alpine corridor;
- Representing at a high-level the road and rail network on the Rhine-Alpine corridor;
- Being configurable to represent the current (base scenario) and future scenarios incorporating the different innovations;
- Being able to estimate the impact of the innovations (and their combinations) on the overall performance of the IWT container logistics chain over the Rhine-Alpine route.

5. Data sources and requirements

Five main datasets are used in the model within the NOVIMOVE project: BIVAS, Destatis, Eurostat, ETIS and AIS. The highest level of detail is provided by BIVAS. Although it covers the majority of the RALP corridor, it does not provide full coverage. Table 3 provides an overview of the geographical

scope of each dataset. The ETIS dataset covers all regions in Europe. Only the edges of the inland waterways of BE, FR, and CH are part of the RALP corridor, therefore it is not needed to collect data on inland flows in these countries. All flows to and from these countries go via DE or NL and are covered by datasets covering DE and NL.

Table 3: Overview of the main dataset used in the NOVIMOVE project

Data source	Disaggregation level	Publishing country	Data format	Confidentiality	Restrictions
BIVAS	UNLO code/port level	NL	.csv, .xlsx	Public	N/A
Destatis	NUTS2, some port data available	DE	.xlsx, .pdf	Public	N/A
Eurostat	NUTS 2 level	EU	.csv, .xlsx	Public	N/A
ETIS	NUTS 3 level	EU	.csv, .xlsx	Public	N/A
AIS	Ship level	Worldwide	.csv, .xlsx	Public	N/A

Each of these data sources is further explained below.

BIVAS

BIVAS⁶ stands for “*Binnenvaart analyse systeem*” (in English: Inland navigation analysis system) and is developed to perform network analyses for inland navigation. The application offers support in answering policy questions on subjects such as taxation of waterways and engineering structures, the effect of blockages, calculating management strategies and maintenance scenarios. The basis of BIVAS is IVS-Next, the vessel traffic monitoring system in NL. IVS90 provides information on all ship movement in the Netherlands including the vessel size, load capacity and cargo transported on the vessel. BIVAS is a software package that uses this data to do network analyses. BIVAS is open source.

BIVAS provides datasets of all ship movements in the Netherlands, including export, import, transit and domestic transport. The dataset has a high level of detail. Per ship journey, there is data on Ship ID, Ship type (CEMT- and RWS classification), ship characteristics (load capacity, width, length, depth), cargo volume (weight, TEU), cargo type (HS-, NSTR- and NST07 classification), origin and destination (UNLO code and NUTS3 region), data and time of departure.

From BIVAS a dataset was compiled of all container flows related to the Rhine Alpine corridor. The dataset covers the year 2017. This year was chosen because it is the most representative of annual inland waterway flows. As mentioned before, in 2018, the water levels of the Rhine were really low, especially during the second half of the year. This significantly hampered inland navigation on the Rhine, especially concerning the ports south of Koblenz. The reason for not choosing data from 2019 has to do with the data reliability issue in that year.

The dataset contains all ship journeys that at some point enter the RALP corridor. From this dataset, all vessels transporting containers were selected. These sum up to a total of close to 40,000 ship journeys carrying containers.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 provide an idea of the size of container traffic along this part of the RALP. While Figure 7 shows the sum of TEU transported per IWW section on the RALP corridor according to the sectioning as defined in BIVAS, Figure 8 provides information on the transshipment points of container ships. Transshipment data is shown in the lowest level of detail available. These are UNLO codes, which represent the level of quays.

⁶ A web application version of BIVAS is available at <https://bivas.chartasoftware.com/Home>.

Figure 7: Freight volumes on the RALP corridor (upper part) per link, as defined in BIVAS.

Figure 8: Handlings in TEU per quay as defined in BIVAS. Data from 2017.

The vast majority of the container flows are port-related. Amsterdam, Rotterdam and Antwerp generate and attract some 5,7 million TEU of container traffic. Over half of the hinterland flows take place in between the ports, are related to one of the Dutch inland ports such as Bergen op Zoom, Moerdijk, Utrecht, Tiel, Gorinchem, or leave the corridor in the south (to Brabant or Limburg via de

Maas) or in the north towards the northern part of the Netherlands. Some 2.8 million TEU travels over the Waal River and continues via the Rhine. BIVAS allows identifying all vessels travelling on a certain section.

Eurostat

Eurostat data is used to fill part of the missing data for the flows. Eurostat’s dataset provides data on IWW container transport flows between NUTS3 regions per NST2007 commodity type. An issue with the dataset is that countries report different numbers for country-to-country flows. For example, Germany reports 608,000 million TEU going from the Netherlands to Germany, while the Netherlands in contrast reports 691,000 million TEU on the same connection. The difference is due to the different methods the country use to process the data. This needs to be kept in mind.

Destatis

Destatis⁷ is the federal statistics office in Germany. It is responsible for collecting, processing, presenting and analysing statistical information concerning the topics economy, society and environment. Destatis publishes statistics on IWW freight transport monthly in its publications and contains

- Origin and destination in German NUTS2 regions and various ports, including Antwerp, Amsterdam, Hamburg, Rotterdam and Zeebrugge, as well as transit through Germany.
- Container traffic passing the borders of Emmerich, Perl/Apach and Neuburgweier/Iffezheim

In earlier Destatis publications, container handlings per inland port were also included. The latest publication dates from 2016. This data is shown in Figure 9. Data from the ports of Strasbourg, Mulhouse and Basel are coming from BIVAS.

Figure 9: Container transshipment along the Rhine.

⁷ DESTATIS data is available at https://www.statistischebibliothek.de/mir/receive/DESerie_mods_00000268

ETIS plus

ETIS provides an O-D matrix for rail, road and IWW transport. The dataset contains transport volumes in tonnes between NUTS3 regions per NSTR commodity type for the year 2010 for IWW and rail and the year 2015 for the road. The dataset is the result of a European project called 'ETISplus' that aimed to create a common dataset of transport flows for EU transport modelling. The road dataset is useful to provide an estimation of the modal shift potential of road freight to IWW transport along the corridor.

AIS data

The automatic identification system (AIS) is an automatic tracking system that uses transceivers on ships. AIS continuously transmits a vessel's position, identity, speed and course, along with other relevant information, to all other AIS equipped vessels within range. Shore stations allow port authorities, maritime safety bodies and others to collect this data as well.

6. Main output identification

On the superordinate logistics system level, the different innovations infused in the DES model are expected to have a certain level of performance on the configured base scenario within the model. The overall expected effect of the NOVIMOVE innovations is illustrated in *Figure 10* in the form of a KPI spider.

Figure 10: Expected overall impact of the innovations within the NOVIMOVE DES model

As seen in Figure 10, the vessel waiting time is expected to drop, by applying for instance a smart navigation solution, and, thus, the turnaround time of inland vessels in ports as well. The total costs are likely to decrease with the implementation of the innovations, especially with the use of the innovative vessels suitable for low-water use. Likewise, the fuel consumption and the emissions generated will presumably sink, by applying for instance the dynamic scheduling services at locks and, thus, adopting smart steaming strategies. Finally, the travel time on the inland waterways is expected to drop due to higher efficiency throughout the entire journey.

7. Conclusion

This paper sets the background of the NOVIMOVE DES model by diving into the market developments of both the supply and demand side of container barge transport, engaging with key stakeholders within the sector to create the system boundary, architecture and key performance indicators for the DES model that is developed. This provides the various stakeholders with a holistic and relevant picture and enables the performance monitoring of the innovations in their respective application context.

This study is the first step towards developing the DES model of the container IWT logistics system. The next step in this study is the development of the logistics cost, time and mode choice submodels to be included in the main model as well as the collection and structuring of the data that will be infused in the main model.

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